

A SPECIAL FEATURE OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF MECHANICS-DRIVERS

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Abstract. *In this article, special attention is paid to the requirements and specific features of professional training of mechanics-drivers. In the professional training of students, great importance is attached to the development of their professional knowledge. Also, in this article, concepts such as "profession", "specialty", "professional training" are highlighted and their content is explained.*

Keywords: *profession, training, specialty, transport, component, vocational training, vehicle, mechanic-driver, military-vocational training.*

The perfect person, that is the development of a person in all aspects, has been the subject of pedagogical research. Accordingly, in the continuous education system, the educational process complements and improves each other harmoniously. Researches show that it is impossible to grow into a fully developed mature person without glorifying goodness, understanding national identity, and feeling a sense of elegance and beauty.

Especially, it is necessary to keep this in mind, in the current conditions, where fierce and uncompromising ideological struggles are taking place on a global scale to conquer the mind, thinking, worldview of the mechanic-driver. Because, the feeling of patriotism, disconnection from national values, seeing the national lifestyle as a thing of the past, blindly imitating Europe, staying in a lifestyle built on modesty, shame, and pride, and entering foreign streets are actually professional preparation. Today's mechanic-driver is showing examples of social activity, he is nurturing, working hard, creating innovative technologies, and striving to gain deep knowledge. They are forming creative, talented, world-viewing young people who know foreign languages perfectly, can effectively use the possibilities of information technology. It is difficult to describe in one word the social, military-professional thinking of young people who are in tune with the times. The development of science and technology, the diversity of lifestyles cannot fail to have an impact on the educational environment. Based on the high requirements of the fast era, it is an important task to follow democratic principles in professional training for a mechanic-driver.

First of all, let's analyze the opinions of scientists in this regard, focusing on concepts such as "profession" and "professional training".

The concept of a profession is an occupation that requires special training, a person constantly experiences and serves as a source of livelihood. The profession unites people engaged in the same activity, and within this activity, certain relationships and moral norms are established.

Research of E.A.Klimov states that "Profession is a necessary and valuable field for society, which requires physical and mental strength from a person". [2]

Specialization is special knowledge in the work process acquired through professional education and training, it is a complex of skills and abilities, which are necessary to perform a certain type of activity within this or that profession. Thus, specialization is a type of activity within the profession. It will be oriented towards personal achievements or the achievement of

common results through specific situations. N.A. Muslimov emphasizes in his search that professional adaptation of the future vocational education teacher is one of the important aspects of his professional formation. It recognizes the following as important pedagogical conditions in this process:

material and technical conditions (educational buildings, educational auditoriums, availability of a set of educational technical means, etc.);

Educational and methodological conditions (state educational standard, educational programs, educational plans, etc.);

Social and educational-technological environment;

And he conducted research on the consistent, continuous and systematic implementation of organizational and educational activities [3].

E. Seytkhalilov explains that "professional training is the process of mastering theoretical knowledge, skills and abilities that allow a person to engage in a specific type of professional activity" [5].

A. Abdukodirov emphasizes that the basis of professional training should reflect "psychological, psychophysiological, physical and scientific-theoretical and practical training of the future specialist". Based on the opinions of the authors, the concept of "professional training" can be defined as follows [1].

The definition of professional training includes professional knowledge and skills in the studied category, it makes it possible to distinguish such indicators as the orientation of a person to culture and society. The competence structure of engineers should include the desire to work in a certain professional field and live in harmony with the environment and others. Thus, the competence of a mechanic-driver includes professional competence and social-psychological competence. In turn, they can be divided into general competencies for all graduates and special individuals important for a particular direction.

Professional training is related to the choice of a specific type of labor activity or field and it is the expression of a clear and conscious decision, and is directly related to the goal-oriented work carried out with the audience. Thus, professional adjustment can be considered as the mutual integration of separate components of the processes that develop the need for professional activity in mechanics-drivers, develop a responsible and creative approach to it, social values motivation, and acquire a direction focused on the individual.

In the scientific researches of the well-known pedagogue and psychologist V.A. Slastenin, the issue of pedagogical activity, the formation of a teacher's personality, in particular, the improvement of his professional skills, was studied in a wide range of directions.

In this place, the pedagogue scientist V.A. Slastenin emphasized the following in the formation of professional skills and qualifications of the future engineer:

specific situations in which the specialist should work;

his work duties;

the need to take into account the required knowledge, skills and abilities.

Pedagogical-psychological aspects of the professional adaptation of personnel. It is appropriate to clarify the content of important concepts and categories within the scope of the subject in the theoretical study, analysis and justification of the social relevance of the research problem. Therefore, in the course of scientific research, we tried to illuminate the pedagogic-psychological aspects of professional adjustment by clarifying the essence of concepts such as

motives for choosing a profession, professional orientation, orientation to the pedagogical profession, pedagogical activity, professional knowledge, skills and abilities, competence.

Professional training - is the level of physiological, psychological and physical preparation of a person for carrying out his professional activity based on the acquisition of special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, as well as spiritual and moral qualities. Formation of professional training is a process of physiological, psychological and physical training of a mechanic-driver to successfully carry out his professional activity, the formation of special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, as well as spiritual and moral qualities in a person based on qualification requirements. Based on the above definitions, we defined the professional training of a mechanic-driver as follows and adopted it as a working definition.

Figure 1. A working definition of the "professional training" of a mechanic-driver

Based on the above, we can note that the requirements and specific features of professional training of mechanics-drivers include the following:

- full use of the technical capabilities of the vehicle;
- to know the requirements determining the location, function, structure, principle of operation, movement (operation) safety of the vehicle;
- Systematize one's actions and behavior;
- formation of skills to apply theoretical knowledge of the profession in practice;
- to live with a goal and to be able to combine future plans with the development of social life in order to achieve the goal;
- types and properties of fuel-lubricants used in vehicles, ways to save fuel-lubricants, increase the service life of tires and batteries, requirements for safety rules during their use and maintenance;
- inspection of the vehicle before departure and on the road, daily maintenance, elimination of minor operational faults that do not require disassembly of mechanisms and aggregates, as well as technical maintenance and seasonal performing maintenance work;
- preparation and current repair of faulty transport vehicles;
- knowledge of general and traffic safety rules in all cases;
- knowledge and practice of the rules of transportation, as well as providing first aid to those injured in a road traffic accident.

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